

Human Resource Information System is a Win –Win Tool to Maintain Work Life Balance in Banks

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ABSTRACT

In this globalised and techno savvy world it is a great challenge to maintain Work Life Balance of employees at all level. HRIS is one of the software which helps employees to achieve work life balance i.e. cost effective recruitment, track data, payroll services and compensation benefits etc. Both primary and secondary data has been collected. The findings revealed that there is positive outcome by using HRIS software in Banks. It is cost effective and efficient software to make productivity.

KEYWORDS: HRIS, Work Life Balance, Bank

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INTRODUCTION

Work Life Balance is a bloodline for any organization. Everyone is so busy in there in there working life they don't have a time for others even for themselves also. Although every company is trying to provide flexibility in working which is a greatest challenge and need for employee retention and attrition. HRIS is one of the software which helps employees to achieve work life balance.

According to Lockwood (2003) WLB means to provide satisfaction, improve morale, retention in the organization and reduce absenteeism in the organization. Conflict between work and family reduce employee morale to work with zeal, limit the opportunities, causal absenteeism, employee turnover, retention and many more.

Time has changed where work and personal life both need prioritize. Satisfaction level of employees plays a great role to sustain in the organization.

Mean of Work Life Balance differs from person to person and organization to organization. As different people have different perception about work life balance policies for their employees. According to Doherty and Manfred (2006) Work life Balance is based on the premise that everyone should have complete life in which sufficient amount of time is given to the personal interest such as (continuing education, social/ community work, sports, hobbies and family interest.

Source- (The economic times)

Human Resource plays a vital role in the organization as all the resources land, labour, capital and machines run by them. HRM practices refer to the activities adopted by the organization for managing organization goals and objectives (Schuler & Jackson, 1987). WLB is a strategic HR issue which needs to be deal very passionately.

Human Resource Information System is one of the software which helps to maintain WLB in the organization. Implementing of this software reduce time ,paper, reduction of error, labour management as software can track employees, monitor their work, identify workforce needs & employee self management etc. HRIS is a like a cobweb that includes a distinct types of HR software. It depends on bank they choose HRIS software according to their needs. According Hendrickson (2003) HRIS is an integrated system used to gather, store & analyze information regarding an organizational human resources. It provides both strategic and administrative functions which helps to maintain Work Life Balance.

Figure- 1(Source- Indiamart.com)

This diagram shows that administrative and strategic function done by HRIS. It is cost effective and time saving software with robust technology.

Human Resource Information System in Banks

HRIS transform the function from manual to automated process. With digitalized era Banks has to be upgraded and updated with the technologies to compete in this period. This software provides such type of functions which is fruitful for the banks to work in lesser time and satisfied employees with Work Life Balance.

Figure-2 (Source- hrpayrollsoftware.Com)

Uses of HRIS in Banks

- 1. Payroll-** This system automate employee attendance records, pay cheques while calculating deduction and taxes. This module calculates automatic deposits and manual cheque writing capabilities. It complies all statutory compliance and labour laws. It encompasses all financial management system.
- 2. Time & Attendance-** HRIS helps in automate collection of employee attendance, entry and exit in office. Advantage of this software is track the employees, working projects and accuracy in data analysis. Standardized time and work related effort.
- 3. Training & Development-** It is an important step for any organization to make their employees learn, knowledge, train, educate, giving skill about the organization for effective working. Globalization transforms the process and policies of banking operations. So HRIS is helpful in providing speedy training and tracking the learning management system which maintains employee performance management system and appraisal.
- 4. Recruitment-** This module includes both internal and external recruit process from hire to staffing position.

Innovative recruitment, hiring skilled & technical employee right person fit with the organization. Both time & cost save recruiting with HRIS software. Smart recruitment helps in focusing soft skill and culture fit evaluation.

- 5. Employee Self Service-** Bring your own service promotes employee engagement & focused worker. Transparent communication enhanced the working & fast deployment of work. The module also lets supervisors approve O.T. request from their subordinates through the system without overloading the task on HR department.

List of the HRIS Software used in Banks

Banks Name	HRIS Software
1. HDFC Bank	Flexcube by Oracle
2. ICICI Bank	Finacle, People Soft
3. Axis Bank	SAP, Finacle
4. Yes Bank	Sun Tech
5. Union Bank	People soft HRMS
6. IDBI Bank	Adrenalin

(SOURCE- Given Banks above own sites)

Review of Literature

According to Nancy R Lockwood (2003), "Work Life Balance Challenges and Solutions", This article deduced that Work Life Balance is a key for any company to increase employee morale, reduce absenteeism, retention etc. Work life programs offer a win win tool to maintain balance between personal and professional life.

According to Pratibha Barik (2016), "Work Life Balance a strategic Human Resource Policies and Practices followed by Indian Organization," This article talks about Work Life Programs i.e. flexitime, parental leaves, childcare assistance and counselling etc which helps to achieve work life balance policies & retention of employees in the organizations. The revolutionary change make the organization compel to maintain work life balance policies to retain and satisfaction among employees.

According to Amber Tariq (2012), "Work Life Balance as a Best Practice Model of Human Resource Management: A Win- Win Situational Tool for the employees and the Organization," This article deduce that how human resource manage work life balance & maintain motivation to work, empowerment & more commitment to the organization. An Exploratory study has been done. Flexibility of working makes employees motivated to work with zeal.

According to M Nishad Nawaz (2014), "To assess the level of employees satisfaction on HRIS usage," This article reveal that employees are satisfied with the usage of HRIS as various aspect got fulfilled i.e. time & cost saving, information flow, HR process i.e. decision making.

According to SubhashC kundu(2012), " Application of HRIS in Human Resource Management in India: A Study," This paper reveal that mostly employee record and payroll function is performed through HRIS. Indian companies and MNCs both are using HRIS at the same extent. It is used in least in performance appraisal and reward management activities.

According to Sabnam Mostari (2018), "Perceived benefits of Human Resource Information System (HRIS) stimulate the efficiency of Human Resource Manager: a study on Banking Sector of Bangladesh," This article deduced that HRIS generate opportunities for employees to retain and satisfaction in the organization. ANOVA, Pearson Correlation and regression analysis has been done. There is need to provide training and enhancement in using HRIS as using the HRIS software result get positive in achieving organizational goal and HR managerial efficiency.

According to Thomas Kalliath (2008), "Work-Life Balance : A review of the meaning of the balance construct," IN this paper 6 conceptualised work life balance role has been reviewed i.e. multiple roles, equity across multiple roles, satisfaction between multiple roles, fulfilment of role salience between multiple roles, a relationship between conflict and facilitation and perceived control between

multiple roles. These all roles describe relationship between employer employees, mediators and result of work life balance.

Research Methodology

- Primary Data (Data from survey) & Secondary Data (Data from Google Scholar, Academia edu, Research Gate, EBSCO & Wikipedia).
- 3 Private Sector Banks were chosen for conducting the research i.e. HDFC Bank, ICICI Bank, Axis Bank.
- Survey is done on the basis of Simple Random Sampling i.e. Probability Sampling.
- Sample Size is 200
- Respondents were HR managers, Assistant professor, HR Executives and General Manager.
- Survey was done through Telephonic conversation and sent emails.
- Result from the survey as follow-

1. HRIS software plays a major role in Bank

	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	50	25
Agree	80	40
Neutral	40	20
Disagree	20	10
Strongly Disagree	10	5
TOTAL	200	

GRAPH-1 (Source- On survey Basis)

Interpretation- The above graph shows the view of respondents that software plays vital role in the Banks. It shows that **25%** respondents were strongly agree, **40%** respondents were agree, **20%** respondents were neutral, **10%** respondents were disagree, **5%** respondents were strongly disagree HRIS software plays a major role in the bank.

2. Automation of HR workflow, software enables the employees in Speedy work.

	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	70	35%
Agree	60	30%
Neutral	20	10%
Disagree	20	10%
Strongly Disagree	30	15%
TOTAL	200	

GRAPH 2 (Source - On Survey Basis)

Interpretation- The above table shows that **35%** respondents were Strongly Agree, **30%** respondents were Agree, **10%** respondents were Neutral, **10%** respondents were Disagree, **15%** respondents were Strongly Disagree that automating HR workflow makes the work speedily and in less time.

3. Reason to use HRIS software

Components	Percentage
1. Reduce paper work	100%
2. Data Accuracy	70%
3. Remove Reduancy	50%
4. Cost effective	80%
5. Time Saving	60%

GRAPH 3 (Source- On Survey Basis)

Interpretation- The above graph shows that excellence in using HRIS software in Banks. As good response is shown from the chosen 3 Banks.

4. Functions followed by using HRIS software

Functions	Percentages
1. Recruitment	100%
2. Payroll	100%
3. Performance Appraisal	60%
4. Training and Development	70%
5. Compensation Benefits	65%
6. Career Development	30%

GRAPH-4(Source- On Survey Basis)

Interpretation- The above graph shows that employees were satisfies with the using above function used by HRIS software used at an immense scale in Banks.

5. Using HRIS software’s helps to maintain Work Life Balance

Benefits	Percentages
Employee Retention	70%
Reduce Absenteeism	40%
Employee Morale	50%
Flexibility in Working	100%
Time Management	60%

GRAPH-5(Source- On Survey Basis)

Interpretation- The above graph shows that using of HRIS software has a great impact in Banks. Implement of this helps to maintain Work Life Balance. 100% employees agree in flexibility in working which is a greatest challenge for the bank.

Objective of the Study

- To find out how HRIS maintain Work Life Balance in Banks.
- To analyze Boon of HRIS in Banks.

Functions of HRIS in Banking Sector

- Helpful in easy maintenance records of employees i.e. personal information of employees, salary, leave application, attendance, compensation benefits & scheduling etc.
- Regular compliance with statutory laws and regulations.
- Learning Management System provided through HRIS software as it gives coaches, training, knowledge and skills how to start with the work. It also gives acknowledgement of orientation programs.
- Flexibility in working as online working can be done like on boarding, recruitment, tracking of employee & store data.
- Automation for better employee engagement, freely communication that helps to work, collaborates effectively and efficiently.

Figure-3 (SOURCE- Google.com)

FACTORS OF WORK LIFE BALANCE

Individual Factors	Organizational Factors	Societal Factors	Other Factors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Personality ➤ Well being ➤ Emotional Intelligence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Work arrangements ➤ Work life balance practices & policies ➤ Organization support ➤ Superior support ➤ Colleague support ➤ Job stress ➤ Role ambiguity ➤ Technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Child care facilities ➤ Spouse support ➤ Family support ➤ Social support ➤ Dependent care issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Age ➤ Gender ➤ Marital status ➤ Parental status ➤ Experience ➤ Employee level ➤ Income ➤ Type of the family

Source- Poulouse, S.,et al.(2014) Work Life Balance: A Conceptual Review.

Findings

- HRIS plays a major role in the Banks. 75% respondents agree it is beneficial to use.
- 100% employees believe HRIS software’s reduce paper work, flexibility in working, payroll and recruitment.
- Implementing of HRIS in Banks provide automation of working and speedily working environment.
- 80% employees agree software provides flexibility in working and 70% employees agree it is cost effective manner.
- Overall in the study it was found out that appliance of HRIS software in Banks has a fruitful result which increases productivity, effective and efficiency in goals.

CONCLUSION

Workforce is the bloodline of any organization so it is the responsibility of the bank to Work Life Balance plans, policies& procedures for their employees towards commitment of the work, boost morale, flexibility in working, satisfaction, reduction in paper work, time saving and employee retention. From the above study it is proved HRIS software helps to accomplish role of Work Life Programs and has positive outcomes has been shown implementing HRIS software’s in Banks. There is need to provide training and giving more knowledge about uses of HRIS.

Limitation

- In this paper only 3 private banks has been taken, more private banks can be taken for better result.
- A comparative study can be conducted between Public Banks and Private Banks.
- Biasness of the result can be possible as Data Analysis in only done through Bar Graphs and Frequency Table.

REFERENCES

- [1] www.scribid.com
- [2] Wikipedia.com
- [3] Sabnam Mostari(2018). Perceived benefits of Human Resource Information System (HRIS) stimulate the efficiency of Human Resource Manager: a study on Banking Sector of Bangladesh, *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, e-ISSN: 2278- 487X, p-ISSN:2319-7668,Volume 20,Issue 12.VerVI,PP 01-09
- [4] Amber Tariq, Muhmmad Asif Tanveer, Hassan Danial Asiam (2012). Work Life Balance as a Best Practice Model of Human Resource Management: A Win- Win Situational Tool for the employees and the Organization, *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, ISSN 2039- 2117, Vol3.
- [5] Subhash C Kundu(2012). Application of HRIS in Human Resource Management in India: A Study, *European Journal of Business and Management*, ISSN 2222-1905(Paper) ISSN 2222-2839(Online) Vol 4, No.21.
- [6] Nancy R. Lockwood (2003). Work Life Balance Challenges and Solutions, *SHRM Research*.
- [7] Pratibha Barik and Dr. B. B. Pandey (2016), Work-life Balance a Strategic Human Resource Policies and Practices followed by Indian Organizations, *International Journal of Management and Social Science* (ISSN 2455-2267), VOL.05, Issue 03, Pg. no. 427-435
- [8] Thomas Kalliath and Paula Brough(2008), Work-life balance: A review of the meaning of the balance construct, *Journal of Management and Organization* 14:323-327, Volume 14 Issue 3.
- [9] Nishad Nawaz(2014) , To assess the level of employee satisfaction on HRIS usage in select software companies in Bangalore Karnataka, India, *Elixir Human Res. Mgmt*.66, ISSN 20438- 20441